

Analysing Bank Statements To User's Need

Prakash R. Vaidya, Sanika Kulkarni, Ojas Kulkarni, Kumar Kolhe, Anuja Kumbhar, Rahul Kuwar

Department of Engineering, Sciences and Humanities (DESH)
Vishwakarma Institute of Technology, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract—In an era where financial management is crucial for individuals. Efficient analysis of banking transactions plays a vital role in budgeting, expense tracking, and financial planning. This website automates the processing of bank statements, transforming raw transaction data into a well-organized, structured and insightful Excel sheet. Daily spending analysis is website built using Python, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, React and Python Flask to help people understand where they are spending their money in order to manage their finances better.

Keywords- Bank Statement Processing, Daily Expenses Report, Excel Sheet Generation, Financial Data Automation, Net Amount Calculation, Withdrawal and Deposit Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Individuals face challenges in managing their finances effectively. People often spend impulsively without keeping track of their expenses, leading to overspending and financial mismanagement. In today's fast-paced world, keeping a close eye on daily spending habits is important for maintaining financial stability. However, most people do not analyse their expenses regularly and when they do, they find it difficult to interpret bank statements. Generally, bank statements are lengthy, unstructured and cluttered which makes it difficult to read the transactions. This makes it difficult to extract meaningful insights which results in poor budgeting and inefficient money management. Also, many of the existing financial tracking websites/app require user to enter transaction details manually which is time consuming and frustrating. Additionally entering the transaction details manually is prone to errors.

This paper presents a web-based solution that automates processing of bank statements and provides a simplified Excel sheet of transactions to use. This platform groups the transactions date-wise and calculates the grand total of withdrawals and deposits for each day. Also counts the number of transactions done per day and determines the daily net amount which helps the user to understand if there is a profit or a loss for that particular day. By avoiding manual data entry and giving a clear breakdown of daily spendings, it allows users to make informed financial decisions.

In this paper we discuss the implementation, development and benefits of our daily spending analysis website. We explore how automation in financial data processing improves decision making and accuracy along with efficiency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In existing, we need to maintain the Excel sheets, CSV etc. files for the user daily and monthly expenses. In existing, there is no as such complete solution to keep a track of its daily expenditure easily. To do so a person has to keep a log in a diary or in a computer, also all the calculations need to be done by the user which may sometimes results in errors leading to losses [1].

This application is an expense tracker that helps users to keep an eye on their expense, and one more feature of this application is cutting down unrequired expenses, which in turn provides a more responsible functioned life style. [2].

This tool maintains and manages data of daily expenditures, providing users with profound knowledge of their expenses. It offers statistical analysis features to help users understand and manage their spending more precisely. [3].

Expense trackers are designed to assist users in recording and monitoring their daily expenditures

and income. They offer functionalities such as categorizing expenses, setting budgets, and providing visualizations to help users understand their spending patterns. For instance, an Android-based application allows users to maintain a computerized diary, enabling them to record income and expenses, and access this information anytime, thereby reducing the effort in handling daily expenses. [4].

Users can effectively control monthly expenses and reduce spending by using the supplied sophisticated expense tracker. Users can build their own categories with matching limits and set a monthly cap. [5].

A robust and user-friendly website enables users to keep a digital journal of their daily expenditures. Users may better comprehend their spending because to the feature's day-wise distribution, which makes it simpler for them to stick to their budget. [5].

This will help you to make a note for what or the things we have to do for the end of month. For example, like how much it expenses for monthly and what are the expenses for a month. Some of the expense features like food expenses billing expenses like phone, electricity, taxation and some other personal expenses. [6].

Research indicates that consistent use of expense trackers can lead to improved financial habits, such as increased savings and more prudent spending. By providing users with a clear picture of their financial status, these applications empower them to make informed decisions and achieve their financial goals. [4].

III.METHODOLOGY/EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis/Algorithm/Design/Method

For creating this website, a structured analysis was done based on the prior existing financial analysis websites and apps used for tracking expenses. Below is a refined outline used for the development of Daily spending analysis.

Research and analysis:

We conducted a comprehensive analysis to find out the problems of users, that they face during analysing their spendings. Due to lack of proper services related to quick analysis people don't understand where and how much they are spending and ultimately, they overspend. Therefore, after

thorough research we came up with a project that helps not only individual but also further can be used for venders and business.

Content strategy:

Layouts, structure of multiple bank statements were analysed and finalized on one of the popular /most used banks that is State bank of India (SBI), to write an appropriate and customized backend code for extracting accurate transaction data and filtering out unnecessary content.

Target audience and their needs were then identified to ensure point functionality. User interface (UI), website functionality, website layout and other features and its goals were then finalized. After experimenting with various codes, designs, ideas and resources, the final back-end code, design of the user interface was drafted. Now, the team was ready for the development of the project.

Testing and Quality Assurance:

Various testing was conducted to ensure the optimum functionality of backend processing, flexibility of website. Many testing methodologies such as unit testing, user acceptance testing and performance testing to identify any issues/bugs were conducted. Changes were then made accordingly.

Deployment and Hosting:

After multiple testing's the website was deployed on local host. Keeping the needs of individuals, in mind, we developed a website considering the factors such as scalability, transparency and server configuration. Proper backup and recovery mechanisms have also been added.

Continuous Improvement and Evaluation:

In order to identify areas of improvement we took surveys and gathered feedbacks from the users. Accordingly, we made improvements in our platform.

Actual Implementation (website images and diagrams): We have already discussed the methods used for designing the website of Daily spending analysis.

Now let's take a look at the display of the figures, images and diagrams of the same.

Fig 1

Fig 2

The design of this website is in such a way that it would be very easy for anyone to use.

It starts with a start page where the user needs to click and it takes the user to the home page. The user then clicks on the 'choose a PDF file' button. On clicking on the 'choose a PDF file' button, a window opens and allows the user to select his/her bank statement that he/she wishes to see the analysis of. After selecting the file, a message 'File selected: file_name' appears confirming that the file has been selected. The user then must click on the 'upload' button. After the file is processed a message 'File processed successfully' appears on the screen, confirming that the file has been processed. Along, with this a 'Download Excel'

option appears on the screen. On clicking this a window opens asking the user if he/she wants to open/save/save as the processed excel file. The 'Contact Us' button is for all the users to enquire about any issue that they are facing; this is where they can ask or complain about various problems faced by them.

DATE	PARTICULARS	WITHDRAWALS	DEPOSITS	TRANSACTION COUNT
Date: 01-10-2024				
01-10-2024	UPI/DR/Bikan Ch/UTB/gay/food...	160.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
Total for the day:		160.00	0.00	Net Amount: -160.00
Date: 03-10-2024				
03-10-2024	UPI/CR/ANAND GA/ICIC/apl/icc/fresh...	0.00	150.00	Transactions: 2
03-10-2024	UPI/DR/Vishwika/PESB/paytm/fresh...	150.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
Total for the day:		150.00	150.00	Net Amount: 0.00
Date: 04-10-2024				
04-10-2024	UPI/DR/IN s Mar/UTB/Nk d...	220.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
Total for the day:		220.00	0.00	Net Amount: -220.00
Date: 05-10-2024				
05-10-2024	UPI/DR/Anket A/PESB/paytm/chi...	40.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
Total for the day:		40.00	0.00	Net Amount: -40.00
Date: 06-10-2024				
06-10-2024	UPI/DR/PUNE NET/HT...	0.00	0.00	Transactions: 4
06-10-2024	UPI/DR/HOTEL SA/PESB/q...	0.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
06-10-2024	UPI/DR/HOTEL SA/PESB/q...	0.00	0.00	Transactions: 1
06-10-2024	UPI/DR/SHREE BA/PESB/q/water...	60.00	0.00	Transactions: 1

IV.CONCLUSION & FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed system will help in eliminating the challenges which are faced by individuals during money management and analysis. The system will have a major impact on the finance industry. The project allows for quick and easy analysis of money on the basis of a bank statement pdf. The

output in which the analysis is provided is in a excel sheet which is a universal format and a powerful tool for analysis of any data.

In future we are thinking of adding many more banks to our website, such as HDFC, PNB, KOTAK, BOM etc. We will also provide a graphical representation of the spending analysis. We will be also launching the website in future.

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